

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FIBRE ARCHITECTURE AND CRACKING DAMAGE IN A KNITTED FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITE.

C.R. Rios¹, S.L. Ogin¹, C. Lekakou¹ and K.H. Leong².

¹ *School of Mechanical and Materials Engineering
University of Surrey, Guildford, GU2 5XH, England*

² *Cooperative Research Center for Advanced Composites Structures Limited
506 Lorimer Street, Fishermen's Bend, Victoria, 3207, Australia*

SUMMARY: The relationship between fibre architecture and cracking damage in a knitted fabric reinforced composite has been studied under tensile loading conditions. A novel technique has been employed to make a sandwich laminate, consisting of a knitted fabric layer sandwiched between two 0° layers. This specimen configuration, together with the transparency of the laminate, enables features of the cracking damage to be related to the fabric architecture.

KEYWORDS: damage development, knitted fabric composites, mechanical properties, crack accumulation.

INTRODUCTION

Knitted fabric reinforced composites are of increasing interest due to the possibility of producing net-shape/near-net-shape preforms, on the one hand, and the exceptional drapeability/formability of the fabrics which allows for forming over a shaped tool of complex shape, on the other [1]. Both of these features follow from the interlooped nature of the reinforcing fibres/yarns. The mechanical properties of knitted fabric are highly orientation-dependent and the final property parameters are also dependent on such factors as the fibre volume fraction and the number of cloths employed to make a laminate [2,3]. Of particular interest in this work is the relationship of the complex fibre architecture to the damage accumulation under load.

Leong et al [4] have shown that knitted fabric reinforced composites can show an accumulation of cracks under load in both the course and wale directions, and that the cracking patterns are different in detail for these two directions. They also attempted to relate the cracking damage to the fabric architecture but this is quite complex in laminates fabricated from multiple layers of fabric.

In this work, specimens have been made with a single layer of knitted glass fabric sandwiched between unidirectional layers. This configuration enables multiple fracture to occur in the knitted fabric prior to failure so that the damage accumulation can be related to the fabric architecture.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The sandwich specimens were fabricated using a single layer of Milano weft-knit cloth produced from E-glass yarns (2x68 tex) (see Figure 1) and a wet impregnation technique. The knitted cloth was cut to size and fixed inside a steel frame using tape around its edges. The frame was placed in a filament winder so that unidirectional glass tows could be wound around the frame to produce the sandwich panel. The glass fibres were impregnated with an epoxy resin (Astor Stag Epoxide Resin; Astor Stag NMA curing agent and Ancamine K61B accelerator). Sandwich panels were made with either the wale direction of the fabric reinforced with unidirectional fibres (termed *wale specimens* below) or with the course direction reinforced (termed *course specimens* below). The panel dimensions were 250 mm x 250 mm and the unidirectional tows on each face of the sandwich panels had a thickness of about 1 mm, with an overall panel thickness of about 3.1 mm. The overall fibre volume fraction of the laminates was 0.29, although the fibre volume fraction within the central (knitted fabric) layer was much lower. Coupons 230 mm long and 20 mm wide were cut from the panels. Aluminium end tags (50 mm long by 20 mm wide) were used for the tests and strain gauges were bonded near the centre of the coupons. An Instron 1196 testing machine was used with a constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Load/strain data were collected using a datalogger.

Figure 1.- Photograph of the knitted fabric indicating the dimensions in wale and course directions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2a shows a typical stress/strain curve for the sandwich specimens loaded in the wale direction and Figure 2b shows the corresponding increase of crack density with strain. For these specimens, crack initiation occurs at a strain of about 0.9% although a significant increase in crack density occurs after a strain of about 1.1%. The crack initiation strain of about 0.9 % is in reasonable agreement with the strain to failure of a single layer of knitted fabric reinforced resin tested alone, which was found to be about 0.8%.

Comparing figure 2a and 2b it is clear that the first “knee” in the stress/strain curve corresponds to the onset of cracking accumulation which produces a crack spacing of about 4 mm. A second “knee” corresponds to the development of a crack spacing of 2 mm.

Figure 2a.- Stress vs. strain curve for a wale specimen.

Figure 2b.- Crack density variation with strain for a wale specimen.

Figures 3a and 3b show similar plots for a course direction specimen. Here, the cracks initiate at a slightly lower strain (about 0.8 %), although the strain to failure of a single layer was found to be a little higher (about 0.9%).

For both the wale and course specimens, the cracks accumulate in a similar fashion to cracks in a cross-ply laminate [5,6]. In the case of the wale specimens however, planar cracks are formed which usually extend from one edge of the coupon to the other. By contrast, in the course specimens, the cracks are much more irregular and appear to be branched at higher strains.

Figure 3a.- Stress vs. strain curve for a course specimen.

Figure 3b.- Crack density variation with strain for a course specimen.

Figures 4a and 4b show a plan view of the wale and course specimens near failure where the difference in the cracking pattern is obvious. As already mentioned above, the cracks in the wale specimens develop initially with a crack spacing of about 4 mm, but subsequent loading produces a saturation crack spacing of about 2 mm (at an applied strain of about 1.8 %). This crack spacing is maintained until specimen failure at about 2.5 % strain, although occasional short cracks do initiate between the major cracks. The course specimens, on the other hand, show a much smoother increase in crack density up to coupon failure (at an applied strain of about 2.4 %) but the crack pattern is much less regular and crack densities in the course specimens are more difficult to measure.

Fig. 4a

Fig. 4b

Figure 4.- Crack density prior to fracture. Fig. 4a, wale specimen;
Fig. 4b, course specimen.

The regularity of the cracking pattern in the wale specimens can also be seen clearly in polished edge sections (Figure 5a). In this view, both the repeating pattern of the fabric (every 4 mm) and the low fibre volume fraction of the central (knitted fabric) part of the sandwich can be seen clearly. The average crack spacing at saturation (at 2 mm) is half the distance of the repeating pattern of the fabric. Such a crack spacing is consistent with cracks forming at needle and sinker loops in the Milano fabric architecture. A similar view of a course specimen near failure (Figure 5b) shows that the average crack spacing of about 1 mm near failure is consistent with the spacing of the sides or legs of the loops. Inspection of the micrographs for the course specimens shows that yarn cross-over points also appear to act as crack initiation sites here (eg at A in the Figure), although more work is required to determine the precise relationship between the cracking pattern and the fabric architecture. In general, the cracks in the course specimens do not extend in a planar manner across the knitted fabric layer. It is this effect, when viewed in the plan view, which gives rise to the appearance of crack branching and causes the crack density to be more difficult to measure.

Fig. 5a

Fig. 5b

Figure 5.- Micrograph of the edge section. Fig. 5a, wale specimen; Fig. 5b, course specimen.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A novel specimen, consisting of a single layer of knitted fabric sandwiched between 0^0 plies enables the relationship between crack accumulation and fabric architecture to be investigated. The technique confirms that cracking patterns in the wale and course directions are different and are related to fabric architecture. Loading in the course direction produces a crack density which increases with strain to failure. For the wale direction, a saturation crack spacing develops which corresponds to the spacing of the needle and sinker loops.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnologia (CONACyT) Mexico for the provision of a studentship for C.R. Rios.

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